

Supplementary Online Material: Quantized thermal conductance in metallic heterojunctions

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Pt and Pt-Ir tips fabrication by electrochemical etching

To etch platinum and platinum-iridium tips, we developed a recipe starting from previously proposed methods^{1,2}. Both groups suggested a two-step approach, comprising a coarse etching step using a relatively high AC voltage (> 25 V RMS) followed by a pulsed fine etching step at lower voltage (< 5 V). The first step is intended to form the main cone of the tip with a radius of a few micrometers, whereas the second forms a sharpened cone on top of the main one with an apex diameter of 100 nm, as shown in Figure 3b. The tips are made out of Pt (99.99+ %) and Pt-Ir (80%-20%) wire with 0.25 mm diameter (GoodFellow). A transformer connected to the power socket supplies an RMS voltage of 25 V at 50 Hz to the metal wire and the graphite (99.99+ %) counter electrode immersed in a 2M solution of CaCl₂, achieving sufficiently high current of around 500 mA. Etching times of about 4 min for platinum and 9 min for platinum-iridium are observed without drop-off. Then, a manual switch placed between the transformer and the counter electrode is used to apply voltage pulses of 2.5 V RMS in intervals of 1 s, achieving apices with diameters of about 100 nm with a good reproducibility.

W tips fabrication by electrochemical etching

Tungsten is another very common material used to fabricate sharp tips by electrochemical etching for scanning tunneling microscopy³. Among all the recipes available in literature, we adopted the method described by Collins⁴, where a wire loop used as a counter electrode is not immersed in solution but contains a thin electrolyte layer, which the tungsten tip can go through. In this way, the etching is localized at the tip area in contact with the solution; the process ends with the drop of the portion below the loop, creating effectively 2 tips. Typically, the tip that falls shows the smallest radius. The technique works with both AC and DC voltages yielding a similar apex diameter of around 50-100 nm. The difference between them lies mainly in the etching time and the shape of the resulting tip cone: using AC modulation, the etching is fast and with bubbles (~ 3 min), forming a conical tip with a large cone angle, while using a DC voltage, it does not generate bubbles but it is rather slow (~ 12 min), giving

tip shapes with high aspect ratio. For the STM-BJ experiments, the AC method is preferable as it provides tips with low aspect ratio, helping the formation of stable junctions.

After the etching, tungsten tips are known to oxidize quickly when exposed to air. There are several known methods to clean the oxide from STM tips, including UHV annealing, chemical treatment using hydrofluoric acid, AC polishing and sputtering⁵. We obtained the best results by cleaning the etched tips by ion milling (10 min, at 500 mA and 600 V). After this step, break junction experiments on a gold substrate yielded quantization peaks at multiples of the conductance quantum G_0 , as expected for Au-Au contacts.

A gold loop is used as a back electrode while the W wire (99.95% - GoodFellow) with 0.25 mm diameter is immersed into a 2M NaOH solution. An AC voltage of 3.5 V at 50 Hz is then applied between the W wire and the gold loop, until the bottom part of the wire drops.

Bibliography

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